

A COMMON, OPEN SOURCE INTERFACE
BETWEEN EARTH OBSERVATION DATA
INFRASTRUCTURES AND FRONT-END
APPLICATIONS

Deliverable 20

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First versions of three front–end drivers

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0.2	2019/07/15	Florian Lahn, WWU Matthias Mohr, WWU	Added R and JavaScript client
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For any clarifications please contact openEO@list.tuwien.ac.at.

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List of Acronyms

API Application Programming Interface

EVI Enhanced Vegetation Index

1 Overview

This deliverable summarises the state of the three 'front-end drivers' for openEO. The term 'front-end driver' is taken from the proposal, but it is more common to describe them as 'client libraries' that facilitate the usage of the openEO web services in certain programming environments. This is necessary as the openEO target audience does not necessarily know how to work with a web service directly. Moreover, these client libraries hide technical implementation details and allow adding some convenience methods to increase the ease-of-use of openEO as a whole.

The three libraries created correspond to the main programming languages that are initially targeted and are publicly available on GitHub:

1. Python: <https://github.com/Open-EO/openeo-python-client> [1],
2. R: <https://github.com/Open-EO/openeo-r-client> [2], and
3. Javascript: <https://github.com/Open-EO/openeo-js-client> [3].

The current version of these libraries support working with openEO back-ends that implement version 0.4.0 of the openEO Application Programming Interface (API) specification. The core design of these libraries is fairly straightforward: the user calls functions or methods from the library, which are translated into the corresponding openEO web service calls and sent to the desired openEO back-end. Likewise, the web service response received from the back-end is translated back again into a result and returned to the user for further manipulation and inspection.

This report accompanies the continually expanding client libraries, which's descriptions are updated regularly. The report, which is accompanied by two other project deliverables (D17: openEO full API implementation, first version; D18: First versions of back-end drivers) describes a practical example of the client libraries' current usage. The example concentrates on a Python code snippet, using the openEO library and on its translated process graph structure. Afterwards, structural differences in the use of the R and the JavaScript clients will be addressed. For further up-to-date descriptions and examples, see the public openEO GitHub repositories [1–3] and the project's living documentation [4].

1.1 Python client

As described above, the Python client allows developers and scientists working in a Python environment to interact with openEO back-ends in a familiar, so called Pythonic way. A noteworthy feature that has been implemented in the Python client, is allowing the user to use simple Python operators to express band math formulas in a very compact way. Below is a Python code example to compute the Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI), which is often used for vegetation monitoring, based on different bands from multispectral satellite images:

```
import openeo
session = openeo.connect("https://example.openeo.org")
bbox = {"west": 16.1, "east": 16.6, "north": 48.6, "south": 47.2}
s2_radio = session.imagecollection("Sentinel-2")\
```


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```
.filter_daterange(extent=["2016-01-01", "2016-03-10"]) \
.filter_bbox(west=5.15183687210083, east=5.153381824493408,
            south=51.18192559252128, north=51.18469636040683,
            crs="EPSG:4326")

blue = s2_radio.band("B02")
red = s2_radio.band("B04")
nir = s2_radio.band("B08")
evi_cube = (2.5 * (nir - red)) / ((nir + 6.0 * red - 7.5 * blue) + 1.0)
result = evi_cube.max_time().download("result.geotiff", format="GTiff")
```

The operations in this code sample are translated behind the scenes into a process graph, illustrated by Fig. 1.1. Note that the band math formula is translated into a separate process graph (on the right of the figure), which is passed into a 'reduce' process. The user of the Python client does not need to know that openEO uses a reduction over bands to implement band math, which illustrates how the client libraries can simplify the usage of the openEO library.

Figure 1.1: EVI process graph.

This example is also included in the updated API documentation [5]. The idea is to lower the learning curve by providing examples in the documentation.

On top of the Python client, a QGIS plugin [6] has been developed to allow users to interact with openEO back-ends directly in their familiar Desktop GIS environment.

1.2 R client

The openEO package for R aims to support scientists to interact with an openEO back-end using R. Other R packages contain only functions that are self-contained, e.g. functions for various statistical analysis. In order to interact with the dynamical systems of openEO back-ends, the package offers two main objects - an openEO client and a process graph builder. The first helps to formulate queries to the web services of the back-end and interprets their results and latter helps to build the process graph.

The R programming way is functional or procedural, which means that you can write scripts that consist of a bunch of commands that will execute your analysis. Usually it is not intended to operate on web services which contain different states like "connected" or "logged in". The main classes are written as R6 objects which is R answer to object-oriented programming and which helps to integrate different states of objects. The specific operations on an openEO back-end are written as individual functions to cope with the average R users experience.

To see an example how the R client interacts with an openEO back-end, please have a look at the GitHub example [7] for calculating a minimum NDVI – a work flow, developed for the Proof-of-Concept (see also [8]) and continuously adapted to the latest openEO version.

1.3 JavaScript client

The JavaScript client is a thin layer on top of the openEO API so that users don't need to know the API in detail and can access it more easily. In contrast to R and Python, openEO does not expect users to run the JavaScript client in an interactive programming environment such as JupyterHub or the command line at the moment. Currently, the JavaScript client is more meant to help developers to implement other tools on top of it. The first example is the web-based Web Editor [9] as an easy-to-use user interface for non-programmers. The second example is the mobile application, which is currently developed by Solenix. Both will be based on the JavaScript client.

The JavaScript client is currently lacking an easy way to build process graphs from the command line. Nevertheless, JSON is natively implemented in JavaScript and as such working with the openEO API is a very easy and intuitive task for JavaScript developers. This is supported by the documentation for the JavaScript client [10].

2 References

- [1] openEO consortium. (2019) Python client api for openeo. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/Open-EO/openeo-python-client>

- [2] ——. (2019) R client package for working with openeo backends. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/Open-EO/openeo-r-client>
- [3] ——. (2019) Javascript client for the openeo api. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/Open-EO/openeo-js-client>
- [4] ——. (2019) openeo documentation. [Online]. Available: <https://open-eo.github.io/openeo-api/index.html>
- [5] ——. (2019) openeo python client usage. [Online]. Available: <https://open-eo.github.io/openeo-python-client/>
- [6] ——. (2019) openeo qgis plugin. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/Open-EO/openeo-qgis-plugin>
- [7] ——. (2019) openeo proof-of-concept use case 1. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/Open-EO/openeo-r-client/blob/master/examples/gee-uc1-example.R>
- [8] E. Pebesma, M. Mohr, J. Dries, M. Schramm, W. Wagner, J. Verbesselt, and C. Briese, “openEO D04: core API prototype including Proof of Concept,” Tech. Rep., Mar. 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2540674>
- [9] openEO consortium. (2019) openeo javascript web editor. [Online]. Available: <https://editor.openeo.org>
- [10] ——. (2019) openeo js client documentation. [Online]. Available: <https://open-eo.github.io/openeo-js-client/0.4.0/>